

Secure management of IoT devices lifecycle through identities, trust and distributed ledgers

D5.4 – Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	101020416	Acronym	ERATOSTHENES
Full Title	Secure management of IoT devices lifecycle through identities, trust and distributed ledgers		
Start Date	01/10/2021	Duration	42 months
Project URL	www.eratosthenes-project.eu		
Deliverable	D5.4 Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings		
Work Package	WP5		
Contractual due date	M26	Actual submission date	30/11/2023
Nature	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Responsible author	Shukun Tokas (SINTEF)	Lead Beneficiary	SINTEF
Authors	Shukun Tokas (SINTEF), Hui Song (SINTEF), Sokratis Vavilis (INLE), Konstantinos Loupos (INLE), Antonio Skarmeta (UMU), Jesús García (UMU), Rosella Omana Mancilla (ENG), Dimitri Van Landuyt (KUL), Christos Xenakis (UPRC), Konstantinos Krilakis (EUL).		
Internal reviewers	ATOS, AIRBUS		

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.1	08/08/2023	2%	Initial Deliverable Structure	Shukun Tokas
v0.2	13/09/2023	30%	Deliverable outline updated, introduction added.	Rosella Omana Mancilla
v0.3	20/10/2023	50%	Task timeline added, Annex I & II added, Phase I training schedule added	Shukun Tokas
v0.4	06/11/2023	75%	Executive summary added, training screenshots added, Planning and execution sections updated.	Shukun Tokas
v1.0	08/11/2023	90%	Conclusion added, executive summary updated, introduction updated.	Shukun Tokas, Rosella Omana Mancilla
v1.1	15/11/2023	95%	Task partner comments addressed	All task partners
v2.0	29/11/023	100%	Internal reviewers' comments addressed	Shukun Tokas, Internal reviewers

Disclaimer

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers and it does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the ERATOSTHENES consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the ERATOSTHENES Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the ERATOSTHENES Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© ERATOSTHENES Consortium, 2020-2025. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	5
2	Introduction	6
2.1	Mapping ERATOSTHENES outputs.....	6
2.2	Deliverable overview and report structure	6
3	Preparatory activities.....	7
3.1	Planning	8
3.2	Creation of training material	8
4	Execution plan for trainings.....	11
4.1	Phase I: Training Pilots.....	12
4.2	Phase II: Training Pilots & users.....	14
5	Conclusion.....	15
6	Annex 1: Template for training materials.....	16
7	Annex II: Module training feedback form.....	17

List of Tables

Table 1: Terms and Abbreviations

Table 2: Adherence to ERATOSTHENES GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Table 3: List of identified technical modules for training

Table 4: Known and potential cybersecurity challenges of technical modules

Table 5: Phase I Modules

Table 6: Phase II Modules

List of Figures

Figure 1: Timeline of Task 5.6

Figure 2: Training schedule for Phase I

Figure 3: Screenshot from TMB module training

Figure 4. Screenshot from SSI module training

Figure 5. Screenshot from TMRA module training

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Table 1: Terms and Abbreviations.

Abbreviation / Term	Description
CTI	Cyber-Threat Information
DBC	Diadikasia Business Consulting
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DTA	Trust Agent Deployer
FedLPy	Federated Threat Analysis
IdM	Identity Manager
IDPS (IDS/IPS)	Intrusion Detection Prevention System (Intrusion Detection System /Intrusion Prevention System)
IoT	Internet of Things
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Description
NIS	Network and Information Security
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
SME	Small-and Medium Enterprises
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TMB	Trust Manager and Broker
TMRA	Threat Modelling & Risk Assessment

1 Executive Summary

This document provides details of preparatory activities carried out to plan for technical module trainings for ERATOSTHENES project. The technical modules and their trainings are designed to strengthen the technical expertise and cybersecurity preparedness of our pilots and users. This deliverable outlines the concerted efforts undertaken during the preparatory phase and outlines a plan for the following training sessions. Anchored by collaborative engagements with pilots in WP5 and through regular pilot collaboration meetings, the task has effectively adopted an approach focused on pilot requirements. This has enabled the identification and alignment of technical modules with the operational requirements of the pilots. This alignment has shown that many of the modules developed in WP2, WP3, and WP4 have effectively been considered relevant & necessary for the pilots. This underscores the strength of our project.

The initiative began with an assessment phase, whereby each pilot's infrastructure was thoroughly analyzed to determine the appropriate technical modules. Purpose of the assessment was to assess the needs of pilots and identify the *technical modules* in ERATOSTHENES deemed relevant to needs of the pilots. Result of this assessment was identification of level configurations of pilot and their mapping with ERATOSTHENES technical modules. For example, in Pilot 1 'Infrastructure monitoring and network traffic analyzing to detect intrusions' configuration was mapped to ERATOSTHENES's *IDS/IPS module*, and 'Protection of vehicle data' configuration was mapped to ERATOSTHENES's *TEE data protector module*. The development of a relevant list of technical modules sets the stage for the preparatory activities that have taken place and the plan for the training phases.

The trainings also play a key role in the feedback loop back to WP2, WP3, and WP4, thereby enhancing quality of documentation, usability improvements, refocusing development efforts for the Phase II trainings. This process also contributes indirectly to WP1 by facilitating the identification of potential gaps in architecture/integration.

In alignment with the decisions made during the kick-off meeting for Task 5.6, our focus for D5.4 and D5.12 will be centered on technical module trainings for project pilots and cybersecurity awareness for the general public. Consequently, we will not be proceeding with cyber security testing facility for each pilot.

Following are the two training objectives:

1. To train ERATOSTHENES's Pilots
 - Ensure that the training aligns with the specific operational needs and configurations of each pilot's domain. And to enhance the technical proficiency of pilots in handling technical modules.
2. To train potential users on ERATOSTHENES outcomes
 - To train general public and users in cybersecurity ecosystem about security of the IoT systems and ERATOSTHENES outcomes.

2 Introduction

2.1 Mapping ERATOSTHENES outputs

Purpose of this section is to map ERATOSTHENES Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Adherence to ERATOSTHENES GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

ERATOSTHENES GA Component Title	ERATOSTHENES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D5.4 Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings	This deliverable will include the preparatory activities and the plan of the cybersecurity exercise execution and training.	Chapter 3, Section 3.1	Chapter 3 outlines preparatory activities, such as module mapping and data collection, undertaken to plan module trainings
TASKS			
T5.6 Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings	This task is to develop the training materials and platforms for different IoT systems, from developers, system operators to end-users, to learn and exercise the cybersecurity-related activities, to maximize the effect of the ERATOSTHENES trust and identity management mechanisms in actual systems.	Chapter 3., Section 3.2 Chapter 4, Section 4.1-4.2	Chapter 3, Section 3.2 outlines the steps followed for creation of training materials and identification of known and potential cybersecurity challenges related to each technical module. This information is relevant for D5.12 (T5.6). Chapter 4, Section 4.1-4.2 outlines execution plans for trainings.

2.2 Deliverable overview and report structure

Section 1 of the deliverable is Executive Summary, which presents the overall scope of the deliverable. Section 2 presents the mapping of ERATOSTHENES Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. Section 3 outlines the Preparatory Activities, describing the engagement with pilots and the subsequent identification of their training needs. This section also details the approach taken to map each pilot's infrastructure to the relevant ERATOSTHENES technical modules. Section 4 presents the Execution Plan for Trainings, dividing the modules into Phase I and Phase II based on their readiness. It details the scheduling and execution of the trainings. Section 5 concludes the report. Section 6, Annex 1: Template for training materials, includes standardized formats for the creation of module training content, ensuring consistency across all training modules. Section 7, Annex II: Module training feedback form, provides the forms used to capture participant feedback on the training sessions, which are essential for assessing effectiveness and identifying areas for improvement.

3 Preparatory activities

To plan for trainings, we started to engage with pilots via pilot collaboration meetings during WP5 tasks and plenary meetings. Purpose of the engagement was to assess the needs of pilots and identify the *technical modules* in the project deemed relevant to needs of the pilots. Task 5.2/WP5 collected content from all pilots about their detailed architecture, flow, hardware specification and technical modules. It included high level configurations of pilot and their mapping with ERATOSTHENES technical modules. For example, in Pilot 1 ‘Infrastructure monitoring and network traffic analyzing to detect intrusions’ configuration was mapped to ERATOSTHENES’s *IDS/IPS Module*; and ‘Protection of vehicle data’ configuration was mapped to ERATOSTHENES’s *TEE data protector module*. This initial assessment of relevant technical modules to each pilot, was followed by several rounds of discussions during pilot collaboration meetings. Based on the initial assessment and feedback from pilot collaboration meetings, we refined that mapping, and identified more technical modules that may be suitable for pilots. Then we had a list of the technical modules deemed most relevant to the operational needs of the pilots. Table 3 presents the complete list of technical modules that require training by the module provider.

Table 3: List of identified technical modules for training.

Module	Pilot	Module provider
TMB	P1, P2, P3	UPRC
FedLPy	P1	ATOS
SSI framework	P1, P2, P3	ATOS
PUF authentication	P1, P2, P3	EUL
DLT	P1, P2, P3	INLECOM
TMRA	P1, P2, P3	KUL
DTA	P2, P3	SINTEF
IDPS	P1, P2, P3	ENG
MUD Management	P1	UMU
CTI Sharing Agent	P1	UMU
Middleware for TEE	P3, P2	KUL
TEE	P1, P3, P2	KUL
Backup and recovery	P1, P3	TUG
Device software repositories	P1	SINTEF
PDP - PEP	P3	UMU
Inter DLT	P2	UMU

3.1 Planning

Planning for conducting technical module trainings is presented in Figure 1. The task begins at M20 with data collection, where templates are created to collect module training data from module providers. In the first round, module providers were requested information, through a shared MS Excel file that included the following fields namely: Module; Part of Module/Framework, Partner; System/equipment requirements? ; Does module need hands-on/workshop training? ; Can module be demonstrated/trained with ppt or pdf? ; Expected duration of training on the module? ; Available for demonstration in Sep 2023? ; Available for demonstration in Phase 2 (i.e., post Sep 2023)? ; Cybersecurity challenges addressed? ; Type/role of user. This information enabled us to (i) decide the feasibility of conducting trainings via Microsoft Teams, and (ii) refine the template for module training data.

Progressing to M25, we reach the milestone of executing Phase I trainings. Training feedback forms are sent out in M26. Feedback is then sought in M27 to inform subsequent activities. Phase II trainings are envisioned in M33-34, where Demo2 training material is developed, leading up to M41, which is reserved for fine-tuning trainings and the preparation of three reports (one from each pilot), aligning with Deliverable 5.12. The timeline illustrates the approach to the training development and the iterative process of feedback integration to enhance the project outcomes.

Figure 1: Timeline of Task 5.6

3.2 Creation of training material

This section presents the data collection process from module providers, underpinned by the deliberate use of templates to streamline the data collection process. The main reason for using templates was to streamline data collection process. Templates can guide module providers to give only necessary information and provide relevant information for follow-up correspondence (i.e., See Annex I for template). Standardized templates were disseminated to all participating module providers to maintain consistency in the material collection process. Training material for all modules listed in Phase I training schedule is collected and stored in a repository. A review was conducted to ensure completeness and clarity of module information. Collectively, this training material will be part of D5.12.

D5.4. Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings

In addition to operational information, specific information about cybersecurity challenges was also collected. The collected cybersecurity information, that source from module providers, is an important component. It encapsulates the known and potential cybersecurity challenges related to each technical module (i.e., see Table 4). Thus it reflects the depth of understanding and preparedness against various cyber threats. This insight has a twofold contribution. It will both serve as a useful resource for informing pilots about various cybersecurity situations and will equip them to navigate and safeguard against the evolving digital threats by using the ERATOSTHENES’s operational framework. This alignment with cybersecurity best practices will be underscored in our final report, demonstrating a proactive and strategic approach to risk management throughout the lifecycle of the project.

Table 4: Known and potential cybersecurity challenges of technical modules.

Technical Module	Known cybersecurity challenge addressed by the module	Potential cybersecurity event/challenge related to the module
PUF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Root of Trust • X.509 forging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impersonation • Man in the Middle
CTI sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for sharing of Cybersecurity information. As per EU’s Network and Information Security (NIS) Directive, sharing CTI is key to achieve significant results in detecting threats and attacks and being able to respond to them. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A cyberattack was detected in the domain and is shared to the outside • A CTI piece is shared from outside the domain and affects the security configuration of the domain
IDPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The IDS/IPS engine is able to detect the major known network attacks, such as DoS, DDoS, Port Scanning, Ping of death, etc. • Huge number of traffic data to monitor and analyse. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main challenge is the increased number of interactions humans have with connected devices that increase of attack surface, Zero-day attacks are the biggest threat: there is no specific and effective countermeasure to a not known threat.
DLT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The DLT module provides solid infrastructure for the distributed, secure and immutable storage of information. • The DLT modules enables the collaboration of organizations by allowing the secure and reliable information sharing among them. Within the ERATOSTHENES contexts, it enables the trustworthy sharing of identity and trust related information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential cybersecurity events are related to the other modules of ERATOSTHENES which use the DLT module (e.g., IdM module). Thus, no DLT specific events are described here.
SSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This task is devoted for providing a secure method to identify an IoT device, using the system information available, generating a unique fingerprint for each device. 	-

D5.4. Cybersecurity Exercises and Trainings

FedLPy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It offers a tool for federated training of models, ensuring data privacy during this process by safeguarding the network traffic. • It allows the IoT network topology to be changed between training runs and allows a limited number of disconnections during a training process. • It continuously monitors the network at device level without the need to fully process the received packets, and it sends alerts to the ERATOSTHENES network to mitigate such threats further. 	-
MUD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security configuration of devices and response to cyberthreats during its lifecycle. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A device is enrolling and needs an initial security configuration • A threat mitigation was devised and needs to be distributed to security domains and applied
DTA	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As part of the recovery process (T2.5), we may demonstrate the recovery scenario where the trust agent is compromised, and a re-deployment action is triggered.

4 Execution plan for trainings

Based on readiness of technical modules, they were segregated into: Phase I and Phase II. Modules that we sufficiently prepared to be demonstrated by September 2023 were listed in Phase I (See Table 5), and rest were listed in Phase II (See Table 6).

Table 5: Phase I Modules

Module	Pilot	Module provider
TMB	P1, P2, P3	UPRC
FedLPy	P1	ATOS
SSI framework	P1, P2, P3	ATOS
PUF authentication	P1, P2, P3	EUL
DLT	P1, P2, P3	INLECOM
TMRA	P1, P2, P3	KUL
DTA	P2, P3	SINTEF
IDPS	P1, P2, P3	ENG
MUD Management	P1	UMU
CTI Sharing Agent	P1	UMU

Table 6: Phase II Modules.

Module	Pilot	Module provider
Middleware for TEE	P3, P2	KUL
TEE	P1, P3, P2	KUL
Backup and recovery	P1, P3	TUG
Device software repositories	P1	SINTEF
PDP - PEP	P3	UMU
Inter DLT	P2	UMU

4.1 Phase I: Training Pilots

Taking into consideration the availability of module providers and pilots, Phase I trainings were scheduled over 3 days; from 09 October 2023 to 11 October 2023. Refer to Figure 2 for the detailed training scheduled. For example, the TMB module training was given by UPRC to Pilots 1-2-3 on 09 October, MUD and CTI module training were requested by only Pilot 1 (Pilot 2 & 3 were invited as optional). IDPS module is integrated with FedLPy module, and it was later realized by Pilot 1 that they are using IDPS, recorded trainings can be accessed for scenarios like these.

Pilots & Technical Module Providers	09 October 2023		10 October 2023		11 October 2023				
	12:00-12:45	13:00-13:45	10:00-10:45	12:00-12:45	13:00-13:45	11:00-11:45	13:00-13:45	14:00-14:45	15:00-15:45
IDIADA / Pilot 1									
Tellu / Pilot 2					optional				
DWG / Pilot 3					optional				
DTA (SINTEF)				DTA					
TMRA (KUL)			TMRA						
IDPS (ENG)									IDPS
FedLPy (ATOS)		SSI				FedLPy			
DLT (INLECOM)							DLT		
TMB (UPRC)	TMB								
MUD + CTI (UMU)					MUD+CTI				
PUF (EUL)							PUF		

Figure 2: Training schedule for Phase I

The trainings were carried out online via Microsoft Teams to foster collaboration and discussion. Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 presents some Screenshots taken during the training sessions.

Figure 3: Screenshot from TMB module training

DLT Architecture

- Identity management
 - SSI based (DIDs)
 - DLT acts as VDR
- Trust management
 - Secure access to Trust Scores
 - DLT acts as VDR
- Smart Contracts
 - Security
 - Flexibility
- Increased efficiency
 - gRPC implementation
 - Based on Hyper Ledger Fabric

Note: DLT has a supporting role for other components, and it is transparent to the end-user.

ERATOSTHENES – Pilot Trainings

Figure 4. Screenshot from DLT module training

Threatened	type	flow	risk	SLE	vuln	LEF	Description
VehicleToTrafficLight	Information...	VehicleToTrafficLight	138,56	10,17	0,512	13,6188	Estimated annual risk of 138,5580395002466A single loss e
Vehicle	Information...	VehicleToVehicle	14,43	0,53	1	27,0282	Estimated annual risk of 14,419102467088776A single loss e
VehicleToTrafficLight	Tempening	VehicleToTrafficLight	14,36	0,51	1	27,8796	Estimated annual risk of 14,351242261508056A single loss e
Vehicle	Repudiation	VehicleToTrafficLight	14,1	0,51	1	27,4766	Estimated annual risk of 14,1015242261508056A single loss e
Traffic Light	Repudiation	VehicleToTrafficLight	14,05	0,53	1	26,7032	Estimated annual risk of 14,049954789019466A single loss e
Traffic Light	Elevation o...	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,96	0,52	1	26,8668	Estimated annual risk of 13,957934401281136A single loss e
Vehicle	Spoofing	TrafficLightToVehicle	13,88	0,51	1	27,2855	Estimated annual risk of 13,853992078654772A single loss e
Vehicle	Denial of S...	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,77	0,53	1	26,9295	Estimated annual risk of 13,770268735959705A single loss e
Traffic Light	Spoofing	TrafficLightToVehicle	13,7	0,51	1	26,6547	Estimated annual risk of 13,699526500326988A single loss e
Vehicle	Spoofing	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,66	0,5	1	27,3496	Estimated annual risk of 13,657689768270426A single loss e
TrafficLightToVehi...	Tempening	TrafficLightToVehicle	13,55	0,5	1	26,8465	Estimated annual risk of 13,5452751335149702A single loss e
Traffic Light	Information...	TrafficLightToVehicle	13,54	0,51	1	26,67	Estimated annual risk of 13,538193173074117A single loss e
Traffic Light	Elevation o...	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,52	0,51	1	26,3623	Estimated annual risk of 13,51964029642148A single loss e
Vehicle	Denial of S...	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,5	0,51	1	26,4212	Estimated annual risk of 13,497939452072982A single loss e
Traffic Light	Denial of S...	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,4	0,5	1	26,5493	Estimated annual risk of 13,491650219980906A single loss e
Vehicle	Elevation o...	TrafficLightToVehicle	13,4	0,51	1	26,302	Estimated annual risk of 13,392414338737295A single loss e
Vehicle	Elevation o...	VehicleToVehicle	13,35	0,5	1	26,5162	Estimated annual risk of 13,34960796025274A single loss e
Vehicle	Repudiation	VehicleToVehicle	13,26	0,49	1	27,01	Estimated annual risk of 13,2585990603609A single loss e
Vehicle	Elevation o...	VehicleToTrafficLight	13,24	0,51	1	25,8473	Estimated annual risk of 13,23969401959551A single loss e

Figure 5. Screenshot from TMRA module training

Phase I training feedback: After each training session, feedback was collected from the pilots to assess whether the participants considered the training to be sufficient, and in case it was not, determine whether another training session would be required, or whether the training material needs to be updated. Feedback included input that would help the partners in charge of the training phase to understand if the template used to collect training data needs to include more information and to inform phase II of training if deemed necessary. For feedback form, see Annex II.

4.2 Phase II: Training Pilots & users

For Pilots: Technical modules that were listed in Phase II (see Table 6), are planned to be trained in M33-M34. Phase II list, if needed can be updated to include more modules. Feedback from Phase I will be used to inform Phase II activities, such as data collection, training material preparation, technical module documentation, etc. .and thus fine-tuning trainings. This process also contributes indirectly to WP1 by facilitating the identification of potential gaps in the architecture and/or integration.

For users: In addition to trainings for Pilots, trainings are also relevant for general public as well as users in cybersecurity ecosystem. This initiative benefits from the collaboration between T5.6 and T6.2. DBC in collaboration with T5.6 team will prepare the training material for the potential users. Target audience for training will be users, who are either interested in or may benefit from ERATOSTHENES outcomes. Training material collected in Phase I & Phase II of T5.6 will be used to prepare training on comprehensive overview of ERATOSTHENES, elucidating its objectives, scope, and the applicability of its components for end users. User training is envisioned in M33-34. Results will be disseminated via social media and a workshop.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable has systematically presented the comprehensive preparatory activities and the strategic plan for the execution of technical module trainings within the ERATOSTHENES project. It has outlined a clear trajectory from the initial engagement and needs assessment with pilots to the planning and creation of training materials, leading to the execution of training sessions in Phase I and the forthcoming activities in Phase II. The report presented the approach adopted to ensure the training is reflective of the specific operational needs of the pilots. The training program aligns with the objectives of enhancing technical proficiency and cybersecurity awareness of project partners and potential users of ERATOSTHENES outcomes. The feedback-based approach to these trainings ensures continuous improvement to evolving the training content and delivery to meet the dynamic challenges within the cybersecurity landscape.

6 Annex 1: Template for training materials

Module Title:

Module Provider:

Version#:

Contact points:

[1-2 person/contributors responsible for the module, to timely reach out to relevant person]

Expected duration of training:

Objective: [A brief statement outlining the primary goal/outcome of the training module]

Background: [Highlight any context or relevant information about the module within the broader scope/vision of ERATOSTHENES.]

----- Module Content -----

Module/Sub-module(s) A1

- **Prerequisites**
 - [List of any tools, software, hardware or other resources pilots should have or be familiar with before setting up the module(s).]
- **Configuration and deployment procedure**
- **Known cybersecurity challenge addressed by the module**
- **Potential cybersecurity event/challenge related to the module**
 - [If possible, provide a brief on a potential cybersecurity event or scenario.]
- **Note/Comment to trainers**

----- Additional Resources & References -----

- **Supplementary Material:**

[Provide any relevant online resources, videos, or webinars that can augment the training. Links to or titles of recommended books, articles, or papers that delve deeper into the topics covered in the module.]

7 Annex II: Module training feedback form

Date:

Pilot Name (Optional):

Module Trained On:

- How would you rate the relevance of the training content? (1-5 scale)
- How useful were the training materials provided to you? (1-5 scale)
- How clear was the explanation of concepts and procedures? (1-5 scale)

- Were there any areas within the module you feel need more in-depth coverage?
- Is there any additional material that you believe should be included?
- Were you able to understand how to apply the training in your (Pilot) context?
- Are there any hands-on or practical exercises you suggest for future trainings?
- Was the allocated time sufficient for the topics covered?
- What suggestions do you have for the upcoming Phase 2 trainings based on your experience?
- Are there specific areas or modules you believe require additional focus?

- Overall, how satisfied are you with the training you received? (1-5 scale)

Additional Comments: *Please provide any other feedback or suggestions that you think could help improve future training sessions.*